

Implementing an Asymptomatic Bacteriuria Management Algorithm

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Problem

- Asymptomatic bacteriuria (ASB) is often misdiagnosed as a urinary tract infection (UTI) and unnecessarily treated with antibiotics.
- ABS overtreatment is associated with:
 - ↑ causative resistant organism isolates (Cai et al., 2015).
 - ↑ C-Diff infection (Belton et al., 2018).
 - ↑ adverse drug reactions & drug-to-drug interaction (Fridkin, 2014).
 - ↑ cost of healthcare (Schultz et al., 2014).

Purpose

Develop, implement, and evaluate an algorithm for health care providers (HCP) and nurses to eliminate unnecessary treatment of ASB in a long-term care facility.

Supporting Framework

Method

- Design: Change project with pre and post evaluation.
- Setting: A 99-bed long-term care facility.
- Participants: Physicians, nurse practitioners, physician assistants, and nurses.

Procedures

- Innovation: An ASB algorithm was developed based on the most current ASB diagnosis and treatment guidelines issued by the Infection Disease Society of America.
- Strategies used to promote the implementation of the ASB algorithm include:
 - In-service class provided to nurses with quiz pre and post.
 - Quality assurance meeting for HCP.
 - Two nursing shift huddles.
 - Posted algorithm in common staff areas.
 - Distribution of pocket-sized algorithm.

Results

Percentage of ASB, UC orders, and antibiotic use pre and post intervention

Note: Abx = antibiotics, N-UTSS = non-urinary tract specific symptoms, OT = overtreatment, RUC = reason of urine culture, UC = urine culture, UTSS = urinary tract specific symptoms.

Results

- After the in-service class:
 - Quiz scores: ↑ from 34.4% to 81.1% (p < 0.0001).
- After implementing algorithm
 - UC ordered routinely without documented reasons: ↓ from 32 out of 65 (49.23%) to 1 out of 15 (6.67%, p = 0.0001).
 - ASB cases receiving antibiotics: ↓ from 20 out of 23 (86.9%) to 3 out of 7 (42.86%, p = 0.0001).

Discussion

- An educational intervention improved knowledge of ASB management as reflected in the increased quiz scores.
- The use of an algorithm facilitated behavioral changes in reducing inappropriate UC orders and unnecessary antibiotic treatment of ASB.
- Nursing staff at the LTCF influenced the changes.

Limitations

- The project took place in a LTCF, with limited beds, HCP, and nurses. The intervention should be further evaluated in larger facilities with more staff participation.

Implications

- The use of an ASB algorithm and an educational intervention is important in the reduction of inappropriate antibiotic use, especially in LTCF.
- Further evaluation in other types of settings will curtail antibiotic overtreatment, which contributes to the development of resistant organisms.
- Nurses play a pivotal role in the process of assessment and treatment of ASB.